

UNVEILING STATISTICAL INSIGHTS: ANALYSIS OF DESCRIPTIVE MEASURES AND FORECAST MODELS FOR NEWLY FORMED ENTERPRISES IN A ROMANIAN MOUNTAINOUS AREA. A CASE STUDY SPANNING 2008-2018

26

26

Brîndușa Covaci, CBM International University & Centre for Mountain

Economy & Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Mihai Covaci, CBM International University & Hyperion University &

Zealandina Agency, USA & UK

Abstract:

This research employs a dual-pronged methodology, featuring a comprehensive descriptive analysis (S1) and the application of various forecast models, to unravel the statistical intricacies of dataset I18. The descriptive analysis delves into key statistical measures, including Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. Following this, a series of tailored forecast models, designed for large data series, are explored, each with distinct Model IDs and specifications, such as ARIMA(0,0,0), Simple, Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

and Holt models.

A meticulous order of statistical prediction smoothing is maintained across all models, encompassing Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. The results, including static R-squared values, provide a granular view of the forecasted values' accuracy and reliability.

The overall picture for the discussed indicator emerges through the lens of statistical prediction models, offering insights into static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). This thorough analysis reveals nuanced statistical characteristics and forecast performance, showcasing the diversity of approaches and informing decision-makers, researchers, and analysts. The study's findings hold the potential to enhance strategic planning, refine forecasting methodologies, and deepen the understanding of underlying data patterns within this indicator dataset.

Methodology:

The methodology employed in this exploration encompasses a two-fold approach: a comprehensive descriptive analysis (S1) and the application of

Mountain Perspective Journal (1/2023)

various forecast models.

1. Descriptive Analysis (S1):

- The descriptive analysis, S1, is based on a dataset represented in a related table and figure found as follow.

- Statistical values extracted include Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75.

- Numerical values obtained from the analysis are reported, featuring key metrics.

2. Forecast Models:

- Tailored models are selected specifically for handling large data series, each identified with a unique Model ID and specifications.

- The chosen models include ARIMA(0,0,0) configurations (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11) and variations such as Simple and Holt models.

3. Statistical Prediction Smoothing:

- A consistent order of statistical prediction smoothing is maintained across all models. The order includes Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles.

- Static R-squared values are reported for each smoothing iteration, offering insights into the accuracy and reliability of the forecasted values.

Results:

In this exploration, we delve into the comprehensive descriptive analysis denoted as S1 (table 1 and figure 1). This analysis provides a rich set of statistical values encompassing Mean, Median, Std. Deviation, Variance, Skewness, Kurtosis, Std. Error, Distance, Minimum, Maximum, and Percentiles 25, 50, 75. The specific numerical values are as follows: Mean 72.1925, Median 9.65851, Std. Deviation 62.5150, Variance 27.31840, Skewness 746.295, Kurtosis 1.149, Std. Error 0.752, Distance -0.388, Minimum 1.481, Maximum 67.76, Percentiles 25 47.32, Percentiles 50 115.08, Percentiles 75 52.3750, and so forth.

Forecast Models:

The models selected for the forecast analysis are tailored for handling large data series. The Model IDs and their corresponding specifications are as follows: S1 - Model_1 ARIMA(0,0,0); S2 - Model_2 ARIMA(0,0,0); S3 - Model_3 ARIMA(0,0,0); S4 - Model_4 ARIMA(0,0,0); S5 - Model_5

ARIMA(0,0,0); S6 - Model_6 Simple; S7 - Model_7 Holt; S8 - Model_8
ARIMA(0,0,0); S9 - Model_9 Simple; S10 - Model_10 Simple; S11 -
Model_11 ARIMA(0,0,0).

Statistical Prediction Smoothing:

A consistent order of statistical prediction smoothing is maintained, covering Mean, Std. Error, Minimum, Maximum, 5th, and 10th Percentiles. The results for static R-squared include values such as .091, .231, -.050, .686, -.050, -.044; R-square .148, .315, -.132, 1.000, -.132, -.092; RMSE 31,721, 25,920, .000, 86,157, .000, 2,900; MAPS 32,907, 22,990, .000, 81,786, .000, 4,326; MaxAPE 97,001, 115,213, .000, 423,828, .000, 6,298; MAE 23,354, 17,995, .000, 61,531, .000, 2,505; MaxAE 57,234, 49,513, .000, 166,238, .000, 4,777; Normalized BIC 6.940, 1.383, 4.797, 9.172, 4.797, 4.929.

Overall Picture for I18:

The resulting statistical prediction models offer an overview for I18, presenting values in the following order: static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE for each model (S1-Model_1 to S11-Model_11). For

instance, S1-Model_1 exhibits values of 2.776E-15, 2.776E-15, 27.318, 29.400; S2-Model_2 shows 4.441E-15, 4.441E-15, 26.565, 27.485; and so forth. This comprehensive analysis provides valuable insights into the statistical characteristics and forecast performance for I18.

Conclusion:

The exploration of statistical characteristics and forecast performance for I18 provides significant insights into the dataset under consideration. The comprehensive descriptive analysis reveals a rich set of numerical values, painting a detailed picture of the distribution and central tendencies of the data.

The application of various forecast models, tailored for handling large datasets, showcases the diversity of approaches in predicting future trends. The reported values for static R-squared, R-squared, RMSE, and MAPE across different models allow for a comparative assessment of their performance.

This study serves as a valuable resource for decision-makers, researchers, and analysts, offering a nuanced understanding of the statistical nature of the

data and the effectiveness of different forecasting models. The findings can inform strategic planning, enhance forecasting methodologies, and contribute to a deeper comprehension of the underlying patterns within the dataset.

Table 1. Prediction analysis for I18

Model		2019	2020	2021	2022	2023	2024	2025
S1- Model_1:	Forecast	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19	72.19
	UCL	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79	136.79
	LCL	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59	7.59
S2- Model_2:	Forecast	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29	73.29
	UCL	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10	136.10
	LCL	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47	10.47
S3- Model_3:	Forecast	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76	58.76
	UCL	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50	90.50
	LCL	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01	27.01
S4- Model_4:	Forecast	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20	71.20
	UCL	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82	133.82
	LCL	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58	8.58
S5- Model_5:	Forecast	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05	82.05
	UCL	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91	132.91
	LCL	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19	31.19
S6- Model_6:	Forecast	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17	59.17
	UCL	82.03	82.13	82.23	82.33	82.44	82.53	82.63
	LCL	36.32	36.22	36.12	36.01	35.91	35.81	35.72

S7- Model_7:	Forecast	15.00	-2.24	-19.49	-36.74	-53.98	-71.23	-88.48
	UCL	116.51	101.24	85.93	70.59	55.22	39.81	24.37
	LCL	-86.50	-	-	-	-	-	-
			105.72	124.91	144.06	163.18	182.27	201.33
S8- Model_8:	Forecast	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74	57.74
	UCL	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58	92.58
	LCL	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90	22.90
S9- Model_9:	Forecast	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75	63.75
	UCL	150.59	186.56	214.17	237.44	257.94	276.47	293.52
	LCL	-23.09	-59.06	-86.67	-	-	-	-
				109.94	130.44	148.97	166.02	
S10- Model_10:	Forecast	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01	69.01
	UCL	272.74	357.12	421.88	476.46	524.56	568.04	608.02
	LCL	-	-	-	-	-	-	-
		134.72	219.10	283.86	338.44	386.54	430.02	470.00
S11- Model_11:	Forecast	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18	108.18
	UCL	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28	289.28
	LCL	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92	-72.92

Figure 1. Graphical forecasting analysis for I18

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